

THE PROJECTIVE REPRESENTATION OF THE FOUR LEVELS OF MIND: SCRIBBLES, DOODLES AND/OR DRAWINGS

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IACT in the early 2000s. She founded Faithfully Love – a Christian counselling and care center for troubled families and school-age children. Both authors have been active in local and overseas training of parents, counselors and therapists. This short article is also completed in remembrance of Yoke Foong Lui, who passed away peacefully in January 2019.

According to the online Oxford Dictionaries, the word “mind” has three meanings: it can refer to “(1) the element of a person that enables them to be aware of the world and their experiences, to think, and to feel; the faculty of consciousness and thought; (2) a person’s ability to think and reason; the intellect; and (3) a person’s attention as well as his will or determination to achieve something” (Oxford University Press, 2019, para. 1-3). The first and second meanings of the mind may include terms like brain, intelligence, intellect, intellectual capabilities, mental capacity. The third meaning also includes inclination, desire, wish, urge, notion, fancy, disposition, intention, intent, will, aim, purpose, design.

However, the term “mind” should not be confused with the other term “brain.” Chia (2012) has differentiated between the two by describing the “brain” as “a tangible organ that ceases to exist once the organism dies” (p.10) ... but the “mind” is “intangible and does not die ... and can be defined as “an organized totality of psychological processes that enables us to interact our environment” (Chia, 2007, p.12). As a result, in this short article, we have chosen to examine the manifestations of the mind through its projective representation in terms of scribbles, doodles and/or drawings at five mental levels: conscious, pre-conscious, pseudo-conscious, sub-conscious and unconscious. We believe that through these markings made on paper we can actually understand an individual’s psyche better, especially his/her socio-emotional state of mind that is imbedded inside or hidden away from the outside.

Scribbles, Doodles and Drawings

In the dialogic-diagnostic art therapies, scribbles, doodles and drawings (see Table 1) are treated as three different forms of printed markings on a given surface regardless of its texture, area and/or size.

Table 1. Markings

Markings	Type	Intent
• Scribble	Graphomotor	No meaningful intent
• Doodle	Grapho-Psychomotor	Partially indicative of mood (e.g., boredom)
• Drawing	Psychomotor	Meaningful intent

According to Kellogg (1969/1970), scribbles constitute basic line formations or markings made by hand “movements showing variations of muscular tension that do not require visual guidance” (p.14). There are 20 basic scribbles (e.g., dot, single vertical line, single horizontal line, etc.) and they are the building blocks of art, and they are important because they permit a detailed and comprehensive description of the work of young children. We consider these scribbles as graphomotor markings rather than psychomotor markings. By graphomotor, we mean the action taken is “pertaining to the muscular movements in writing” (Dictionary.com, 2019, para.1), such as making a marking 0 that resembles letter O, or lines // \ that resemble a pair of parallel lines with a figure 1 sloping downward to the right. Diagram 1 is an example of scribbles done by a two-year-old child.

Diagram 1. Scribbles

However, such markings (as shown in Diagram 1) made may mean nothing to the young drawer as these scribbles are made randomly without any meaning in mind. As for psychomotor, we mean the action taken is “of or relating to a response involving both motor and psychological components” (Dictionary.com, 2019, para.1). In this case, some form of meaningful marking is created to represent something; for instance, two horizontal parallel lines = to represent an equal sign.

Next, there are doodles (see Diagram 2). They are markings made while the drawer’s attention is otherwise occupied. According to Wikipedia (2019), “[D]oodles are simple drawings that can have concrete representational meaning or may just be composed of random and abstract lines, generally without ever lifting the drawing device from the paper, in which case it is usually called a ‘scribble’” (para.1).

Diagram 2. An Irregular Scribble

Scribbling and doodling are early markings, which lack hand-eye coordination and are at the lower mental or cognitive development, are often associated with toddlers and young children between 2 and 4 years of age. Hence, it is not surprising to see “young children struggling to keep their coloring attempts within the line art of the subject” (Wikipedia, 2019, para.2). However, it is also not uncommon to observe such behavior with adults, who do it jovially, out of boredom, as well as those with developmental coordination disorder.

Drawings are more advanced forms of psychomotor markings that take many different forms from a wide range of meaningful schemata such as person (see Diagram 3), house, tree, animal of all kinds (see Diagram 4), and many other objects. From these drawings, several projective drawing techniques have been developed and also used as standardized assessment tools in determining drawers’ mental or cognitive maturity (Reynolds & Hickman, 2004), general intelligence (Flanagan & Motta, 2007) as well as the state of emotional disturbance (Naglieri, McNeish, & Bardos, 1991), which includes internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems (Crusco, 2013).

Diagram 3. A Single Human Figure Drawing

For example, in the single human figure drawing as shown in Diagram 3 above, it provides information about the drawer’s self-concept, which also includes his feelings, nurturance, obsessions, etc. (Chia & Ng, 2011). Notice the absence of ears, eyelashes, arms and hands (as well as elbow), legs and feet (as well as knee) suggests the drawer’s refusal to hear what others are talking about him (without ears) (Klepsch & Logie, 1982), aggressive tendencies (without eyelash) (Machover, 1949), powerless (without limbs), inadequacy and ineffective (Klepsch & Logie, 1982), lacking in support and immobile in the current situation (beyond his control) (Chia & Ng, 2011; Klepsch & Logie, 1982).

In the next example is a drawing as shown in Diagram 4 below, the drawer had chosen to draw a porcupine, which is a pre-

eminent symbol of self-protection and self-defense. The drawer felt a lack of support and being vulnerable to the outside world such that he could become disheartened and frustrated with himself. He could also become very sensitive to uncalled criticism.

Diagram 4. Drawing of a Porcupine

From these psychomotor markings (including erasure and omitted parts of any schema, e.g., a person or an animal), drawings can tell us a lot about the drawer’s socio-emotional state of mind as well as personality in addition to his/her current level of cognitive or intellectual maturity. We have formulated a chart showing the projective representation of the mind according to its five levels of mental lucidity (see Chia & Wong, 2019, for detail) and matching them with our proposed interpretable levels of observable graphomotor and psychomotor markings, provided with some examples (see Table 2 on the next page).

Briefly, the five levels of mental lucidity are (1) Conscious mind, (2) Pre-Conscious mind, (3) Pseudo-Conscious mind, (4) Sub-Conscious mind, and (5) Un-Conscious mind. Each of these levels has been described elsewhere in another paper (see Chia & Wong, 2019, for detail) published in *Unlimited Human!* As for the interpretable levels of markings, whether they are graphomotor or psychomotor type, we have divided them into the following five levels with brief self-explanatory observable markings and some examples:

- (1) Ground level, which matches with the conscious mind and it is divided into two sublevels #C1 and #C-2;
- (2) Surface level, which matches with the preconscious mind and it is also divided into two sublevels #PC-1 and #PC-2;
- (3) Interface level, which matches with the pseudoconscious mind and it is also divided into two sublevels #PSC-1 and #PSC-2;
- (4) Deep level, which matches with the subconscious mind but unlike the other three earlier levels, it has three sublevels #SC-1, #SC-2 and #SC-3; and finally,
- (5) Abyssal level, which matches with the unconscious mind and it has only one sublevel #UC-1.

**Every cell in your body
is eavesdropping on
your thoughts.**

Deepak Chopra

Table 2. The Projective Representation of the Mind

LEVELS OF MENTAL LUCIDITY	INTERPRETABLE LEVELS OF MARKINGS	OBSERVABLE GRAPHOMOTOR & PSYCHOMOTOR MARKINGS	EXAMPLES
CONSCIOUS MIND (C)	Ground Level #C-1	Surface scribbling, doodling and/or drawing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifiable scribbles • Recognizable doodles • Resemblant drawings
	Ground Level #C-2	Recognizable schemata from the scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal • House • Other Building(s) • Tree • Person • Other People • Other Object(s)
PRECONSCIOUS MIND (PC)	Surface Level #PC-1	Size of the scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big • Medium • Small • Tiny
	Surface Level #PC-2	Compartmentalization of scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Box • Encapsulation • Semi-Enclosure
PSEUDOCONSCIOUS MIND (PSC)	Interface Level #PSC-1	Vertical placement of the scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top • Middle • Bottom
	Interface Level #PSC-2	Horizontal placement of scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Left (Past) • Centre (Present) • Right (Future)
SUBCONSCIOUS MIND (SC)	Deep Level #SC-1	Identifiable kinetic or akinetic aspects of the scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Movement(s) or motion(s) • Identifiable tasks/deeds
	Deep Level #SC-2	Signs and Symbols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sign(s) • Symbol(s) • Totem(s)
	Deep Level #SC-3	Chromatic aspects of the scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary colors • Secondary colors • Tertiary colors
UNCONSCIOUS MIND (UC)	Abyssal Level #UC-1	Omitted schemata which are supposedly to be there but are absent in the scribbles, doodles and/or drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial erasure • Total erasure • Omission

The purpose of this projective representation of the mind is to show the dialogic-diagnostic art therapists as well as allied therapists or counselors how they can interpret the meanings imbedded or hidden in the scribbles, doodles and drawings. It is often very difficult to delve in-depth into the subconscious mind of a client, whose desires, ideas, thoughts and wishes (or ditwis for short; also known collectively as urges) (Chia & Lee, 2017) have been deeply repressed over a long period of time. While psychotherapy and hypnotherapy may help to bring these ditwis to surface, this can only be achieved if the client is cooperative or receptive to either of or both forms of therapy. As a result, the dialogic-diagnostic art therapies may offer the client an alternative approach to seek professional help so long as it is comfortable or acceptable to him/her.

Conclusion

We have heard this many a time before: “A picture is worth a

thousand words.” This is an English language adage, which means that a complex idea can be conveyed with just a single picture. In other words, a picture can convey its essence more effectively than a wordy description does. In order to reach out to a client, say with some emotional disturbance, the projective drawing technique may be an excellent tool to touch his/her inner self without having to talk so much. To the one who has drawn the picture, it means more than just words to describe a drawer’s ditwis. The picture or drawing as a whole constitutes just a small part of the drawer’s overall psyche. There are many more artefacts to be uncovered from the same picture/drawing for they are speaking in silence to be hearkened with the eyes, not with the ears. Therefore, a dialogic-diagnostic art therapist or counselor must always be mindful or sensitive to these visual details awaiting to be heard visually!

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How To Use a “New Technique...”

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my wife and partner, learned from Jason Linett that you never use the word TEST just before a test of trance or depth of trance. Why not? Too many persons today have negative feelings on that word because they or their offspring are forced into too many tests in school. Try instead “Prove to yourself...” While you are at it, also examine how you greet a Client, keeping in mind the examples shown above.

And you want to improve your acceptance of this new habit? Use it every day, even in non-hypnosis situations. We all know that Advertising and Politics are based on persuasion and the same mechanisms covered in this discussion. Instead of letting Madison Avenue, TV, and the Political Discourse make this their monopoly, begin using it yourself. But remember to use it judiciously – out-and-out lies always backfire. Negative approaches do not work. Use Waking Hypnosis positively and it will assist in your practice.

Remember, three cups, one cup, three cups, one cup, three.... Easily achieved and it will build your confidence.

CONFIDENCE, SINCERITY, LOGIC, AND AN INTENDED BENEFICIAL OUTCOME !!!

Disclosures

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